

FORMATION OF A COMMUNICATION SYSTEM IN THE FUTURE PRIMARY CLASS TEACHER

Karimova Jahona

1st stage master of Tashkent State
Pedagogical University named after Nizami

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10403543>

Abstract. *This article is about the formation of a communication system in a future primary school teacher, the teacher's personal qualities, the moral level of a primary school teacher*

Keywords: *pedagogical communication, free pedagogical activity, simplification of the communication process, conflict situations, communication styles, spiritual and moral norms.*

It should be noted that the realization of the possibilities of communication culture of young students is largely determined by the personal qualities of the teacher. The method of pedagogical communication culture, chosen correctly in all respects, corresponding to the spiritual level and unique characteristics of the primary school teacher, helps to solve the following set of tasks:

Firstly, special attention and friendliness to the young student in communication simplifies the general process of communication with the class team, prepares the ground for the teacher's free pedagogical activity, easily resolves conflict situations;

Secondly, organizing interaction with each child on the basis of free communication, choosing pedagogical and psychological communication methods appropriate to their age characteristics, opens the way to know their psyche, to "enter" their inner world;

Thirdly, the spiritual and moral norms of the future teacher in pedagogical communication are the key to success, increase the effectiveness of education, ensure the teacher's satisfaction and peace of mind at all stages of communication.

"Pedagogical communication culture" in the organization of the educational process in general education schools is a force that directs the direct interaction of teachers and students towards a certain goal. In this case, the future teacher should study the following situations in his professional activity:

- The teacher's adherence to the culture of communication from the very beginning of his educational activities, in this process, he plans daily interactions with the teacher and the group of young students according to the situation, paying attention to the tone of every action, speech, traditional mastering the best features of communication;

- On the basis of communication, to record various situations in the class group, to evaluate the students' behavior by comparing it with the previous state and the state after the educational activity;

- Analyzing the results of one's own communication style from a critical point of view, continuously eliminating the shortcomings. Creating the necessary words, pleasant tone of voice, behavior;

- It is not enough to know its conditions for the effective development of the culture of pedagogical communication, it is the beginning of interaction with young students typical of the "teacher-student" tradition and solving important tasks based on the exchange of ideas attract the object's attention;

- What should be understood by the object of communication, that is, to attract the attention of young students? This means that the future teacher demonstrates his skills with his politeness, culture, good manners, the ability to find a way to the hearts of students in communication, and lays the socio-psychological basis for the organizational forms of communication culture is to get

In order to have a pedagogical effect based on the indicated situations, special requirements are placed on the future teacher's culture of pedagogical communication, ethics and manners, cordiality, communication etiquette. These qualities are a guarantee of success in the future teacher's ability to communicate with parents, organize and manage educational activities with students in the classroom.

The ongoing scientific research shows that a young teacher who follows the culture of pedagogical communication, which is a unique quality of professional activity, should embody the following characteristics:

- A socially-politically active person with high spiritual level views, strong and stable faith, loyalty to the ideals of our state, national idea and ideology of independence, patriotism, self-sacrifice formed in accordance with the socio-political demands and needs of our country;

- Sincere love for young students, the formation of skills and competence to understand all their needs, interests, motives of behavior, behavior;

- Pedagogical observation of events in society, events in the world, nature, existence, interpersonal, inter-group, inter-ethnic relations, the ability to aspire to innovation, creative research;

- Rational understanding of the characteristics of people's behavior and relations in all aspects of pedagogical activity, forming a reflexive attitude towards one's own activity;

- To react rationally and intelligently to any emergency situations, news happening in the society and social and economic changes, to be able to set the right goals, make a plan, direct control, managing and being able to show their capabilities;

- Demonstrate the ability to organize and manage public actions in pedagogical activities, group relations in the public system;

- The breadth of the worldview and scope of thinking, the wideness of his interest in learning worldly knowledge, his tendency to scientific research, his specific scientific potential and the level of pedagogic skills are regularly increased;

- Ability to communicate with young students, logically concise, meaningful, impressive power of speech culture, armed with methods of psychological influence.

The young generation in our country is physically and mentally mature as a priority direction of state policy. At the center of attention, of course, independent thinking, creative and high the goal of perfecting a spiritual person is embodied. Uzbekistan 5 proposed by the President of the Republic Sh.M.Mirziyoyev. In an important initiative, work in the social, spiritual and educational spheres is renewed. The tasks set on the basis of the system require the implementation of important measures related to the education of young people.

In the spiritual, moral and aesthetic upbringing of the young generation, the nation is national educational methods, values and traditions of great world thinkers' worthy contributions to civilization, fruitful of rich spiritual heritage its use will certainly give its positive result. Therefore, education at the core of the concept is "mind of the student (practical of a social nature). To the emotional and mental spheres that inspire activity) and character the idea of influencing in

order to form a certain guide, concept, principle, valuable direction that provides the necessary conditions for the development of a person.

Educational institutions, family and neighborhood in personal development, mass media, internet system and general public Propaganda is important. Future elementary school national and universal values, humanitarianism, patriotism, hard work, philosophy as an important factor of education in the spirit of high faith, it is based on the combination of psychology, pedagogy, history, language and literature sciences. Advanced experiences in national education science primary grade to turn teachers into active participants of social society creates wide opportunities. In this case, "the highest spiritual and embodying physical perfection", "in our modernizing society raising a healthy generation", "forming the spirituality of a free citizen", "It is perfect by raising spiritual and educational work to a high-level education to achieve the goal of "raising people to adulthood" is the essence of the methodology. The state policy aimed at the education of spiritually mature and mature youth is closely related to the methods of spiritual and moral education, and this process is the independent thinking of students at all levels of the continuous education system, especially in the higher education system, is carried out in order to increase creativity and intellectual potential. In this regard, the following comments of our President Sh.M.Mirziyoyev are worthy of attention: "All reforms and changes, large-scale programs implemented in our country are aimed at a single and great goal. He will make our children mature and well-rounded in all aspects consists of educating". When it comes to organizing the creative activities of future elementary school teachers, it is appropriate to define what creativity is, and then choose the criteria for organizing creative activities. The concept of "creativity" is considered the analytical basis of many sciences. It is important that this ability is clear in determining its meaning takes place. The concept includes "creative attitude", "creative activity", "creative labor", "creative person", "creative identity" and other meanings is enough.

To the concept of creativity by many philosophers at the end of the 19th century views are put forward, each of them has its own individuality and diversity of thinking is noticeable. Consequently, creativity is "social a person who creates important new material and spiritual values activity". "Creativity is aimed at eliminating contradictions is one of the manifestations of human activity, for which it is objective (social, moral) and subjective personal conditions (knowledge, skills, creative abilities) etc. is necessary, its result is innovation and progress. "Creativity is an activity of new material and spiritual values its occurrence is its result."

Humanity's self-awareness as a subject of creativity is creativity new directions of considering problems and concepts determined. Philosophers understand the essence of human creative activity, epistemological and they study the problems of general methodological features. Accordingly, to solve the problem of "CREATIVE MAN" in local philosophy of the 20th century the goal of the attempt led. "Creativity" for further substantive description of creative pedagogical activity - it is necessary to refer to the concept of creativity, which is under consideration the central link of the category is counted. One of the developers of the theory of creativity is E. P. Torrens, who defines creativity as the process of emergence of sensitivity to problems, lack of knowledge, their inconsistency, inconsistency; Dj.Gilford distinguishes four factors of creativity on the basis of his model: originality, semantic flexibility, figurative flexibility and semantic spontaneous flexibility in the creative activity of future elementary school teachers. insufficient methodological support for organization;

- along with directing students to creative activities in the educational process including development of communicative competence and related to the field seminar-training and master classes aimed at mastering the news that transfer is not given importance;

- information on tasks and exercises related to creativity effective use of technologies, e-learning resources attention to the formation of knowledge, skills and competences in creating lack of focus, etc.

"Teacher's Pedagogical Creativity" by V. I. Zagvyazinsky in his book creative activity "creating a new pedagogic system, unknown discovery of laws, new ideas, methods, tools; create new to create by awakening the powers of man's inner essence" definition is given. The following is the creativity of the pedagogue from the scientist's side different aspects are highlighted:

1. Strictly defined and limited in terms of time. If in class if an unexpected situation occurs, the teacher will make a new decision in a short period of time must accept.

2. Since pedagogical creativity is integrally connected with the educational process, it should always bring positive results. Cons and it can only be based on imaginary tests and assumptions.

3. Pedagogical creativity is always a collaborative creative work.

4. A significant part of creativity is publicly presented to people (own mental state management skill) is implemented.

It is a professional necessity for every young teacher, who is just starting his career in general education schools, to be able to convey correct, effective information to elementary school students and convince the interlocutor. The future teacher's culture of communication and the breadth of his spiritual world are important in this. Pedagogical activity of teachers is continuous, he should pay serious attention to the following directions while regularly forming the culture of pedagogical communication:

1. Self-awareness from the point of view of high pedagogic activity, (knowing his own qualities, positive and weak points regarding mutual exchange of ideas in communication) and, on this basis, educating himself by means of mutual exchange of ideas.

2. In interaction with people, he develops his communicative ability, exercises the intuition of correct prediction based on communication, how others (teacher team, students, parents) evaluate his ideal visions and capabilities in communication. analysis of reflexive imaginations.

3. Working on the basis of specialized exercises for the development of important features of communication etiquette.

4. Carrying out various public works aimed at educational goals with young students and parents, improving pedagogical organization skills based on mutual exchange of ideas.

5. Forming skills to overcome negative situations that arise in the process of communication, creating a system of situations that develop cordiality and politeness.

REFERENCES

1. Ortikov A. Speech culture and the art of oratory. - Т.: "Dono Qamro" scientific center, 2002. - 78 p.
2. Основы педагогического мастерства: Уч. Пособие для студентов пединститутов /Под ред. И.А.Зязюна.-М.:Просвещение, 1989.- 302 с.
3. Палтишев Н.Н. Педагогическая гармония: Учебно-методическое пособие. - Киев: Магистр-С, 1996.- 104 с.

4. Якушева С.Д. Основы педагогического мастерства: Учебник.-М.: Издательский центр «Академия», 2012.- 256 с.